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3 ***Microcystin as a Biogeochemical Cycle:***
4 ***pools, fluxes, and fates of the cyanotoxin in inland waters***

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18 Keywords: cyanotoxin, cycling, ecosystem

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20 **Data Availability**

21 This is a literature synthesis from previously published data by other authors. The collated values
22 from the literature and proper citation are in the Supplementary Information. The calculated or
23 collated values used in the analysis are available through the Environmental Data Initiative at
24 <https://tinyurl.com/2gnbqagw> The code and tabulated values for models and figure generation
25 can be found at https://github.com/goodgracious23/microcystin_cycle and will be archived at
26 Zenodo upon acceptance of the manuscript.

27
28 **Author Contribution Statement:** Both authors conceived of the study, undertook the literature
29 synthesis, drafted and revised the manuscript.

30
31 **Scientific Significance Statement**

32 There is a pressing need to understand the dynamics of microcystin, a toxin produced by some
33 cyanobacteria, in the environment. Despite substantial advancements in our understanding of
34 individual pools of microcystin, we lack a synthesized understanding of the sources, sinks, and
35 movement of cyanotoxins within aquatic ecosystems. Using a literature synthesis approach, we
36 developed a conceptual biogeochemical cycle of microcystin in lakes. We identified and
37 synthesized the magnitude of four major pools of microcystin in lakes and reservoirs and nine
38 major fluxes, including into the terrestrial environment (another major pool). Through this
39 literature synthesis approach, we also identified understudied pools and fluxes. Adopting the
40 framework of a ‘microcystin cycle’ can provide new insights for the management and mitigation
41 of microcystin exposure risks.

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44

45 **Abstract**

46 Microcystin poses a serious threat to aquatic ecosystems and human health. There is a pressing
47 need to understand the production, movement, and storage of microcystin in lakes. We
48 constructed a conceptual biogeochemical model for microcystin through a comprehensive
49 literature synthesis, identifying four major pools and nine major fluxes in lakes that also connect
50 to the terrestrial environment. This conceptual model can be used as the framework for
51 developing ecosystem mass balances of microcystin. We propose that the concentration of
52 microcystin in the water column is the balance between the import, sediment translocation,
53 production and degradation, uptake, burial, and export. However, substantial unknowns remain
54 pertaining to the magnitude and movement of microcystin. Future investigations should focus on
55 sediment fluxes, drivers of biodegradation, and seasonal dynamics. Adopting the framework of a
56 ‘microcystin cycle’ improves our understanding of processes driving toxin prevalence and helps
57 to prioritize strategies for minimizing exposure risks.

58

59 **Introduction**

60 The widespread eutrophication of inland waters combined with a changing climate is
61 modifying the magnitude and severity of cyanobacteria blooms in some, but not all, waterbodies
62 (Ho et al. 2019; Wilkinson et al. 2022). Cyanobacteria blooms can pose a serious threat to
63 aquatic ecosystems and public health, particularly through the production of toxins that have the
64 capacity to disrupt ecosystem services. Cyanotoxins create unsafe conditions for recreational
65 water use and impede provisioning services such as fisheries, irrigation, and drinking water
66 supplies (Carmichael and Boyer 2016). While there are numerous cyanotoxins, microcystin is
67 among the most prevalent in inland waters (Rastogi et al. 2014). Microcystins are a group of
68 monocyclic heptapeptides produced by numerous genera of cyanobacteria in both marine and
69 freshwater ecosystems. Given the ubiquity of this toxin, persistence in the environment, and the
70 potential for severe harm to humans and wildlife, there is a pressing need to understand the
71 dynamics of when, where, and how microcystin is produced, transformed, moves, and
72 accumulates.

73 As microcystin produced in the water column is a key reservoir and pathway for human
74 exposure, a major research focus has been documenting the incidence and magnitude of
75 microcystin concentrations in the water column (Loftin et al. 2016) and the environmental

76 conditions that lead to microcystin production (Orihel et al. 2012; Harris et al. 2014). There has
77 also been substantial effort to identify the organisms and processes that metabolize microcystin
78 into less harmful molecules (Dziga et al. 2013; Schmidt et al. 2014; Massey and Yang 2020).
79 Additionally, there has been effort to understand the accumulation, transformation, and
80 movement of microcystin in the aquatic food web (Kozłowski-Suzuki et al. 2012; Flores et al.
81 2018), sediments (Zastepa et al. 2015; Wood et al. 2020), and the terrestrial environment
82 (Ibelings and Chorus 2007). However, despite substantial advancements in our understanding of
83 these individual pools of microcystin, we lack a synthesized understanding of the sources, sinks,
84 and movement of cyanotoxins within aquatic ecosystems.

85 Our objective was to develop a biogeochemical model for microcystin from an ecosystem
86 perspective that synthesizes production, movement, and storage in lakes. While our focus here is
87 on lakes, the conceptual model we propose is adaptable to other aquatic ecosystems, including
88 both marine and freshwater environments. Conceptual models of biogeochemical cycles provide
89 a framework for examining the transport and transformation of molecules within and among
90 ecosystems, including the interactions between abiotic and biotic components of the ecosystem.
91 In addition to the more common elemental cycles, biogeochemical frameworks have recently
92 been used to study contaminants such as plastic pollution (Hoellein and Rochman 2021),
93 revealing important pathways for future research. We used this conceptual model to synthesize
94 the current knowledge of the magnitudes of microcystin pools and fluxes in lakes, revealing gaps
95 in our understanding of microcystin dynamics. By taking a comprehensive literature-review
96 approach, we have been able to identify which pools and fluxes are well studied in lakes and
97 which dynamics have received less attention, despite being potentially important pathways for
98 human exposure. Additionally, this conceptual framework can provide new insights for the
99 management of microcystin exposure risks to humans and wildlife.

100

101 **Constructing the Microcystin Cycle**

102 To construct a comprehensive cycle of microcystin for inland waterbodies, specifically
103 focusing on lakes, we reviewed and synthesized the current information on microcystin pools
104 and fluxes in the literature. We performed a literature search in Web of Science using the terms
105 “microcystin*” and “lake*”, which returned 1781 articles. We supplemented this search with
106 additional results by searching for “microcystin*” with “sediment*”, “macrophyte*”,

107 “degradation*”, and “aerosol*”. Each article’s abstract was reviewed to determine if the study
108 contained information pertinent to our synthesis goals and had measurements from an inland
109 waterbody. For studies that were deemed potentially pertinent based on the abstract, the main
110 text was reviewed and if a pool or flux was measured, the estimate of the magnitude was
111 extracted along with details about the ecosystem and methods (see Supplementary tables). In
112 most studies, the magnitude was reported as a range of measured concentrations. We then
113 synthesized this information to estimate the range of microcystin concentrations, the fluxes into
114 and out of each pool, compare the magnitude and rates to biomass turnover times, and identify
115 any gaps in our understanding of the processes that control microcystin dynamics within the
116 pool. In total, we synthesized the quantitative results from 160 studies (see Supplemental
117 Information). While microcystin production and cycling also occurs in marine environments, we
118 chose to limit the literature synthesis to lakes for this study (with some studies also reporting
119 results for reservoirs). However, the conceptual microcystin cycle (pools and fluxes) that we
120 constructed from this review is generally applicable across the aquatic continuum.

121 From our literature review, we identified four major pools of microcystin within lakes:
122 *A. water column*, *B. sediment*, *C. macrophytes*, and *D. aquatic consumers* (letters correspond to
123 major pools in Figure 1, Figure S1). Each of these major pools can be further divided into sub-
124 pools based on the form (e.g., intercellular, extracellular in the water column and sediments) or
125 trophic guild (e.g., zooplankton in aquatic consumers) that contribute to the dynamics in their
126 major pools. These major pools are connected to each other and the *E. terrestrial environment*
127 (another major pool with sub-pools) through nine major fluxes (numbered 1-9 in Figure 1).
128 These fluxes can be broadly categorized as *cellular* fluxes including lysis and several forms of
129 degradation, *food web* fluxes including consumption (direct ingestion or inhalation), excretion,
130 and uptake (osmotic equilibration with biotic tissues), and *transport* fluxes including
131 sedimentation, resuspension, aerosolization, and hydrologic import and export through surface
132 and groundwater movement.

133 Based on this literature synthesis, we propose that concentrations of microcystin in the
134 water column (the most frequently measured pool) are the balance between the import,
135 translocation from the sediments, internal production of microcystin and the degradation, uptake,
136 burial, and export of microcystin. In other words, water column concentrations are not reflective
137 of intercellular microcystin production alone. Below, we describe each major pool including the

138 sub-pools and fluxes that connect them and the environmental conditions that drive accumulation
 139 or loss from each pool.

Cellular Fluxes

- 1 Cell lysis
- 2 Degradation
 - a) biodegradation
 - b) photodegradation
 - c) depuration

Food Web Fluxes

- 3 Consumption (inhalation or ingestion)
- 4 Excretion
- 5 Osmotic uptake

Transport Fluxes

- 6 Sedimentation
- 7 Resuspension/ Diffusion
- 8 Aerosolization
- 9 Hydrologic Import/Export

140
 141 **Figure 1.** A conceptual model of the microcystin cycle in lentic inland waters. The major pools
 142 (A-E) of microcystin and sub-pools (white boxes within major pools) are labeled in the diagram
 143 in light grey boxes. The major fluxes among these pools are denoted with the color-coded
 144 arrows. The numbers on the arrows correspond to the key of fluxes below the figure. The fluxes
 145 (arrows) are between the major pools and inclusive of all sub-pools unless arrows specifically
 146 connect two sub-pools (e.g., the diffusion flux [#7] between the extracellular sediment sub-pool
 147 and the extracellular water column sub-pool).
 148

149 **A. Water Column Pool**

150 **Sub-Pools in the Water Column**

151 Microcystin is synthesized within the vegetative cells of cyanobacteria, forming the
152 intercellular pool of microcystin. When microcystin-producing cyanobacteria are blooming
153 (experiencing exponential population growth), the pool of intercellular microcystin in the water
154 column can increase if toxigenic strains dominate the assemblage. When cells are lysed or
155 damaged, intercellular microcystin is released into the extracellular microcystin pool. In its
156 extracellular form, microcystin can adsorb to particles and organic matter or be subject to further
157 degradation and loss from the ecosystem due to ultraviolet radiation or bacterial metabolism
158 (Munusamy et al. 2012; Massey and Yang 2020). High microcystin concentrations in lakes and
159 reservoirs, reported as the intercellular, extracellular, or combined total concentrations, are
160 associated with eutrophic conditions and low N:P ratios in the surface waters which favor
161 cyanobacterial dominance (Orihel et al. 2012; Harris et al. 2014). Additionally, warmer water
162 temperatures and greater water column stability are conditions that favor cyanobacterial blooms
163 leading to higher microcystin concentrations in the water column (Mantzouki et al. 2018).
164 However, given the dynamic nature of blooms, the size of the microcystin pool in the water
165 column is also dynamic.

166 Assessing the likelihood that a measurable pool of microcystin is present in the water
167 column is challenging given the dynamic nature of cyanobacteria blooms and other fluxes
168 (Figure 1). Large, randomized surveys can provide a snapshot of microcystin pools among
169 hundreds, or even thousands of lakes (Loftin et al. 2016), whereas longitudinal studies on a
170 smaller number of waterbodies are more likely to capture brief episodes of toxin production. To
171 quantify the incidence of a measurable microcystin pool in the water column of lakes and
172 reservoirs, we compiled studies that reported surveying at least five waterbodies for microcystin
173 concentrations. Surveys reported either intercellular, dissolved, or both concentrations combined
174 for the water column. We used the information reported in these papers to calculate the
175 percentage of waterbodies with detectable microcystin pools in the water column for each
176 survey. In total, we reviewed 67 studies that reported on 69 surveys (Table S1). We did not
177 discriminate among survey designs (e.g., statistically randomized, longitudinal, opportunistic);
178 however, if microcystin was detected during any point in a repeated sampling design, the
179 waterbody was considered to have detectable microcystin concentrations. We also categorized
180 the frequency of sampling as reported in 62 of the survey as repeated (>2 sampling events in
181 each waterbody) or snapshot (1-2 sampling events only in a waterbody). Ten of the studies did

182 not provide enough information to determine which waterbodies had detectable microcystin,
 183 only the fraction of samples that had measurable concentrations. For these ten studies we
 184 calculated the percent of samples with detectable concentrations. The collated data is available
 185 from Wilkinson and Shingai (2022).
 186

187
 188 **Figure 2.** The percent of waterbodies (blue) or water samples (teal) with a) detectable
 189 microcystin from 69 surveys ranked from lowest to highest percent detected among surveys, and
 190 b) the relationship between the number of waterbodies in each survey and the detection rate of
 191 microcystin in the water column ($\% \text{ detected} = 111.06 - 27.4 \times \text{waterbodies in survey}$, $p\text{-value}$
 192 < 0.001 , $R^2 = 0.27$), and c) boxplots of the detection rate for repeated sampling surveys and
 193 snapshot (1-2 sampling events maximum) survey designs. There is a significantly higher
 194 detection rate among the population of repeated sampling surveys compared to the population of
 195 snapshot surveys reviewed in this study.
 196

197 Among all the surveys, the presence of a microcystin pool in the water column ranged
 198 from 7.3% to 100% of waterbodies or samples, with a median of 78% and mode of 100% (Figure
 199 2a). This tallying exercise illustrates the ubiquity of microcystin in the water column of lakes and
 200 reservoirs. There was a significant negative correlation between the number of waterbodies or
 201 samples in a survey and the detection rate of microcystin (Figure 2b; F-value = 25.5, $p\text{-value}$
 202 < 0.001 , $R^2 = 0.28$). We hypothesized that this relationship was likely the result of survey design:
 203 surveys of many lakes are more likely to be spatially randomized with a single sampling event
 204 whereas surveys with a smaller number of lakes are more likely to be longitudinal with repeated
 205 sampling events on the same waterbodies. Based on the sampling designs reported, studies with
 206 repeated sampling designs had a significantly higher percent detection of microcystin in the
 207 water column than studies with a ‘snapshot’ design (Figure 2c; one-way ANOVA $F_{1,60} = 5.365$,
 208 $p\text{-value} = 0.024$). Additionally, snapshot surveys had a significantly higher number of

209 waterbodies sampled compared to repeat sampling surveys (one-way ANOVA, $F_{1,60} = 6.03$, p-
210 value = 0.017, number of waterbodies in each survey log-transformed). These findings support
211 the hypothesis that the likelihood of microcystin being present in a waterbody sampled at one
212 single point in time is lower than the likelihood of microcystin being present at any point over
213 time in a waterbody sampled repeatedly.

214

215 ***Water Column Fluxes and Fates***

216 The pool of microcystin in the water column has many potential fates (Figure 1). Two of
217 the major fates for both intercellular and extracellular microcystin are degradation and transport
218 into and out of the ecosystem through surface and groundwater flows, withdrawals for human
219 use, and aerosolization. Additionally, microcystin can be lost or gained from the water column
220 pool with connections to the sediment, macrophyte, and aquatic consumer pools, detailed in
221 sections below.

222 *Degradation Fluxes:* Microcystin is removed from aquatic ecosystems through both
223 photo- and biodegradation. Photodegradation rates are highest at ultraviolet wavelengths
224 (Thirumavalavan et al. 2012) and lead to the rapid and efficient loss of extracellular microcystin
225 from surface waters (Wörmer et al. 2010) (Table S2). This may be a particularly important
226 mechanism in large shallow lakes with a high ratio of surface area to volume. The presence of
227 humic substances may shield microcystin from photodegradation or act as a photosensitizer
228 increasing degradation (Welker and Steinberg 2000). Biodegradation, performed by bacteria and
229 fungi using hydrolytic enzymes to cleave the cyclic structure is another process that leads to
230 substantial loss of microcystin from aquatic ecosystems (Dziga et al. 2013; Schmidt et al. 2014).
231 Microbes that degrade cyanotoxins reside in both the water column and sediments and can even
232 co-exist with cyanobacteria cells themselves (Dziga et al. 2013). Among ecosystems, the
233 abundance of microcystin-degrading microbes is tightly coupled to microcystin availability,
234 highlighting the important relationship between these two bacterial communities (Lezcano et al.
235 2018).

236 Based on rates reported in the literature, the average half-life of microcystin in the
237 environment ranges from 0.5 – 22 days (Table S2). Many studies report a lag phase between the
238 introduction of microcystin in the environment and peak degradation rates (Lezcano et al. 2018).
239 Variation in the conditions that favor higher rates of biodegradation such as warm temperatures,

240 high pH, nutrient availability, and an oxic environment also contribute to the variation in rates
241 among ecosystems and over time (Chen et al. 2010; Dziga et al. 2019). However, much of the
242 information on microcystin biodegradation rates comes from studies performed in a water
243 treatment setting. While advances have been made in isolating and identifying microcystin-
244 degrading bacteria in waterbodies, additional data are needed to understand the seasonal
245 dynamics and rates of biodegradation in aquatic ecosystems to adequately model the magnitude
246 of this important flux at an ecosystem scale.

247 *Transport Fluxes:* In addition to endogenous production of microcystin, toxins produced
248 outside of the ecosystem can be imported from upstream and exported from the ecosystem
249 through hydrologic flows and human transport of water. The relative importance of surface
250 hydrologic connections on microcystin import and export fluxes is likely higher in river
251 networks with reservoirs (Graham et al. 2012; Ge et al. 2021) and marine coastal habitats
252 connected to inland waters (Miller et al. 2010; Umehara et al. 2019). Microcystin can also be
253 exported from a waterbody into the surrounding groundwater (Yang et al. 2016; Zhang et al.
254 2021) and be produced by cyanobacteria active in the vadose zone; however, it is unclear how
255 sediment sorption dynamics might influence this flux (see below). Further research is needed to
256 quantify the magnitude and seasonality of hydrologically driven import and export fluxes of
257 microcystin from waterbodies. Human water export for drinking, irrigation, and transport (e.g.,
258 ballast water) can also alter the size of the water column microcystin pool.

259 Besides hydrologic and human transport, microcystin also leaves waterbodies and enters
260 the atmosphere through the formation of spray aerosols. Wave action, mainly driven by wind,
261 entrains air into the water resulting in the formation of bubbles that eject cyanobacteria cells and
262 extracellular microcystin into the atmosphere upon bursting (Plaas and Paerl 2021). There is
263 evidence that droplets are enriched in hydrophobic congeners of microcystin relative to the bulk
264 concentration in the water (Olson et al. 2020). These droplets, commonly formed by wave action
265 along the shoreline, can be inhaled by terrestrial organisms, including humans. The concentration
266 of microcystin in spray aerosols from lakes ranges from 0.0018 to 50 ng m⁻³ (Table S3), based on
267 the few measurements reported in the literature. Ultraviolet radiation and ozone can quickly
268 degrade microcystin contained in aerosols (Jang et al. 2020). The residence time of microcystin-
269 laden aerosols in the atmosphere, the distance traveled by aerosols, and the dynamic nature of
270 cyanobacteria bloom and aerosol formation all influence the magnitude of this flux yet are

271 largely unresolved for freshwater ecosystems.

272

273

274

275 **Figure 3.** The concentration of microcystin in various pools in comparable units ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry
276 weight, d.w.; note the asterisk indicating the few measurements in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ wet weight, w.w.). Each
277 line or point is a single study of concentration, with the line spanning the range of values
278 reported in the study. For animals, light blue lines are microcystin concentrations in muscle
279 tissue (common tissue for human consumption) and dark blue lines are concentrations in the
280 whole body (consumption-based exposure through predation). Concentrations in other tissues
281 (e.g., liver, hepatopancreas) are listed in Tables S6 and S7.

282

283

284 **B. Sediment Pool**

285 *Sub-Pools in Sediment*

286 The bulk sediment pool of microcystin varies by orders of magnitude, from undetectable
287 to 3 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight (d.w.) among lakes and over time (Figure 3, Table S4). The microcystin in
288 the bulk sediment pool can be divided into microcystin bound in cells—either in biofilms,
289 senesced, or dormant cells and colonies—dissolved in the pore water, and sorbed to sediment
290 particles. The formation and persistence of microcystin-producing biofilms varies, but light-rich,
291 shallow waters favor the development of cyanobacterial mats. The intercellular concentration of
292 microcystin in biofilms ranges from 0.06 – 16 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w. (Figure 3, Table S4).

293 In the dissolved form, microcystin can be found in the pore water between sediment
294 particles. Microcystin can also adsorb to sediment particles, although there is a large range in
295 maximum sorption capacity from 0.004 – 11.9 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w. (Table S4) with some of the variation
296 in sorption attributable to variation in congeners (Maghsoudi et al. 2015) and pH (de Maagd et
297 al. 1999). In general, fine particles such as clay and sediments with high organic matter content
298 have higher sorption capacity for microcystin (Munusamy et al. 2012).

299

300 *Sediment Fluxes and Fates*

301 As evidenced by the numerous sub-pools of microcystin in the sediments and the fluxes
302 into, among, and out of these sub-pools (Figure 1), the sediments are an important component of
303 the microcystin cycle. However, there have been few ecosystem-level investigations of sediment
304 microcystin fluxes (Song et al. 2015), limiting our understanding of the role of this pool in
305 ecosystem dynamics and human exposure risk, overall. One of the main fates of microcystin in
306 the sediments is biodegradation. Biodegradation rates in the sediments are generally higher than
307 the water column, with rates as high as 35 times faster in the sediments of some eutrophic
308 ecosystems compared to the water column (Li et al. 2016).

309 The sedimentation of microcystin-containing cells and colonies contributes to the biofilm
310 pool. Through resuspension and migration, approximately 0.8 – 3% of colonies reinvade the
311 water column (Feng et al. 2019), moving microcystin from the sediment pool into the
312 intercellular water column pool. The rate of microcystin resuspension and residence time in the
313 water column is not well quantified but could be a cryptic pathway of human exposure when

314 water column production is otherwise low. Intracellular microcystin in the sediment pool is
315 susceptible to movement into the extracellular pool through cell lysis or consumption and
316 subsequent excretion by aquatic organisms (see “D. Aquatic Consumer Pool” section below).
317 This dissolved pool in the sediments is subject to either diffusion back into the overlying water
318 column, adsorption to sediment particles, or degradation by bacteria. In a rare comparison of
319 rates within an ecosystem, Zastepa et al. (2017) found that the rate of microcystin diffusion from
320 the sediments, at $1.38 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$, was substantially higher than the burial rate, 0.13 ± 0.18
321 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$, in Lake of the Woods (North America), indicating that the sediments were a potential
322 source of microcystin to the water column (Table S4).

323

324 **C. Macrophyte Pool**

325 ***Sub-Pools in Macrophytes***

326 Macrophytes accumulate extracellular, dissolved microcystin into their roots, stems,
327 leaves, flowers, seeds, and bulbs (Romero-Oliva et al. 2014) with concentrations up to $16.9 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$
328 d.w. in some instances (Figure 3, Table S5). The allocation of microcystin among tissues within
329 aquatic plants varies by species; however, the highest concentrations of microcystin are typically
330 found in the roots and likely taken up from the sediment pool (Song et al. 2009). In addition to
331 microcystin found within their tissues, macrophytes also provide the structural support for
332 epiphytic cyanobacteria growth. While there is limited information regarding microcystin
333 production by epiphytic cyanobacteria, reported concentrations vary from $1.16 - 3.12 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w.
334 of epiphyte biomass (Figure 3, Table S5).

335

336 ***Macrophyte Fluxes and Fates***

337 The rate of microcystin uptake by macrophytes spans orders of magnitude ($1.9 - 544 \mu\text{g}$
338 $\text{L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$; Table S5), with much of the variability attributable to time since exposure, variation
339 among species, and variation in uptake rates of microcystin congeners (Romero-Oliva et al.
340 2015). While the capacity for macrophytes to accumulate microcystin make them a potentially
341 large sink of cyanotoxin in the environment, there is evidence that microcystin exposure can
342 inhibit macrophyte growth by inducing physiological stress (Ujvárosi et al. 2019), potentially
343 altering the strength of this sink. Once incorporated into the tissues of macrophytes, microcystin
344 is removed from this pool through biotransformation and degradation (Table S5) (Pflugmacher

2004; Romero-Oliva et al. 2015), consumption of macrophyte tissues by organisms, release during plant decomposition, or incorporation into the sediment pool upon senescence.

347

348 **D. Aquatic Consumer Pool**

349 ***Sub-Pools of Aquatic Consumers***

350 Aquatic consumer sub-pools include zooplankton, macroinvertebrates including shellfish
351 and emergent insects, and vertebrates including fish that span trophic levels (Figure 3).

352 Microcystin is incorporated into the tissues of aquatic organisms, particularly primary consumers
353 (Papadimitriou et al. 2012), either through direct consumption of intercellular toxins, osmotic
354 uptake of extracellular toxins, or consumption of lower trophic levels that have microcystin in
355 their tissues. While direct toxicity to aquatic consumers is not usually widespread at lower
356 microcystin concentrations, sub-lethal effects such as disruption of reproductive development
357 (Zhang et al. 2019), increased sensitivity of juveniles (Gérard et al. 2005), and genotoxicity
358 (Juhel et al. 2007) can all have population-level effects that influence ecosystem processes
359 (Gérard et al. 2009).

360 Zooplankton are a key link in the aquatic food web between intercellular microcystin in
361 the water column and higher trophic levels (Rohrlack et al. 1999). Primary consumers such as
362 zooplankton mainly accumulate microcystin through direct consumption of cyanobacteria cells.
363 Cladocera such as *Daphnia* graze on phytoplankton in the water column and ingest intracellular
364 microcystin through filter feeding. Whole-body concentrations of microcystin are up to an order
365 of magnitude higher in *Daphnia* compared to other aquatic invertebrates (Figure 3, Table S6)
366 and can have adverse and sometimes lethal consequences for *Daphnia* (Rohrlack et al. 1999).
367 Alternatively, microcystin exposure is hypothesized to provide medicinal protection against
368 some parasites *Daphnia* (Sánchez et al. 2019).

369 In macroinvertebrates microcystin is introduced to tissues through consumption of cells
370 and osmotic uptake of extracellular toxin through trans-tegument diffusion, oral water uptake,
371 and gill or pulmonary breathing. While microcystin is detectable within whole-body tissues
372 (Figure 3), the highest concentrations in macroinvertebrates are usually found in the
373 hepatopancreas and intestines (Table S6). Species that feed by ingesting sediment accumulate
374 larger amounts of extracellular microcystin that is sorbed to sediment particles (Lance et al.
375 2010). Non-selective feeders may have higher susceptibility to microcystin accumulation;

376 however, some macroinvertebrates have developed means for expelling, instead of ingesting,
377 toxins (Juhel et al. 2006). Environmental and dietary exposure over longer periods of time can
378 increase microcystin accumulation, however juveniles can have lower rates of accumulation, in
379 part due to their less developed immune systems (Gérard et al. 2005).

380 Fish accumulate microcystin through epithelial uptake, direct consumption of
381 phytoplankton, and bioaccumulation from prey (Zhang et al. 2009a; Flores et al. 2018). While
382 studies of microcystin accumulation in fish most commonly evaluate concentrations in liver and
383 muscle tissues (Figure 3), a recent meta-analysis of fish tissues revealed that the toxin is also
384 found in the blood, heart, reproductive organs, gut, gills, and skin of fishes (Flores et al. 2018)
385 (Table S7). The highest reported concentration of microcystin contained within fish tissues was
386 $375.3 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w. in the liver of planktivorous smelt (Flores et al. 2018). Microcystin
387 accumulation in fish varies by species and location but is positively correlated with microcystin
388 concentrations in the surrounding water column (Poste et al. 2011; Flores et al. 2018). Feeding
389 strategy also influences microcystin accumulation with higher concentrations in omnivorous fish
390 compared to planktivorous and piscivorous fishes.

391

392 *Aquatic Consumer Fluxes and Fates*

393 Microcystin bioaccumulation is consistently observed in zooplankton, planktivorous
394 fishes, and bivalves (Kozłowsky-Suzuki et al. 2012; Gobble et al. 2016). The rate of microcystin
395 accumulation in aquatic consumers depends on animal behavior and environmental factors. For
396 example, in zooplankton accumulation rates vary depending on environmental effects on filter
397 feeding rates (e.g., temperature) as well as population-level adaptations to cyanotoxins such as
398 avoidance of ingesting intercellular microcystin following exposure to the toxin (Tillmanns et al.
399 2011; Wojtal-Frankiewicz et al. 2013). Population-level effects of microcystin accumulation on
400 fitness are also possible if the toxin accumulates in the reproductive tissues with the potential to
401 be passed on to future (Zhang et al. 2007).

402 Predation is another flux of microcystin between aquatic consumers that leads to
403 bioaccumulation, however there is limited evidence that microcystin biomagnifies in the food
404 chain (Papadimitriou et al. 2012; Kozłowsky-Suzuki et al. 2012). In some food chains there is
405 evidence of microcystin biodilution (decreasing concentration with increasing trophic level), but
406 this does not appear to be common. The potential flux of microcystin from prey to predator is

407 dependent on the tissues consumed. Toxins are often concentrated in digestive organs such as the
408 stomach, intestines, liver or hepatopancreas (see Tables S6-S7). As such, consumption of the
409 whole organism will likely result in higher microcystin exposure than consumption of muscle
410 tissue alone (e.g., humans consuming fish fillets).

411 Once consumed or absorbed and incorporated into organismal tissues, microcystin is
412 excreted, egested, or undergoes biotransformation (i.e., depuration), resulting in detoxification
413 (Schmidt et al. 2014). Biotransformation resulting in detoxification has been documented in
414 *Daphnia* tissues (Wojtal-Frankiewicz et al. 2013), in the digestive glands of macroinvertebrates
415 (Schmidt et al. 2014), and in fish (Flores et al. 2018). Excretion is another flux from aquatic
416 consumers to other pools including the water column and sediment. While microcystin excretion
417 has been documented in fish and other organisms, the sedimentation of fecal pellets and
418 concentration of toxins is not well quantified.

419

420 **E. Terrestrial Environment**

421 ***Sub-Pools in the Terrestrial Environment***

422 Microcystin has been found in the tissues of many terrestrial animals, with the highest
423 concentrations in aquatic-associated wildlife including waterfowl, turtles, and reptiles (Figure 3;
424 Table S7). Microcystin can also accumulate in crops via contaminated irrigation water. An assay
425 experiment to investigate bioaccumulation of microcystin in lettuce (*Lactuca sativa L.*) revealed
426 that toxin the accumulated in the foliar tissues of the plants regardless of the concentration in the
427 irrigation water (Romero-Oliva et al. 2014). There is also evidence that microcystin can
428 accumulate in soils (Zhang et al. 2021). In livestock, microcystin can accumulate through
429 watering from a microcystin-contaminated source and potentially be passed to other terrestrial
430 consumers.

431

432 ***Terrestrial Fluxes and Fates***

433 Microcystin found in terrestrial environments mainly originates from the water column
434 and aquatic consumer pools. Originating from the water column, microcystin aerosol
435 concentrations vary widely with bloom and wind conditions, but this is generally a diffuse flux.
436 Microcystin-laden water withdrawn for drinking or irrigation purposes introduces the toxin to
437 terrestrial consumers (i.e., wildlife, livestock, humans) and soils (Zhang et al. 2021). Animal

438 movement between the aquatic and terrestrial environment (e.g., insect emergence and human
439 recreation) as well as predation are another flux between these spheres (Moy et al. 2016). Of
440 particular concern are the fluxes of microcystin that create cryptic pathways of human exposure.

441 Humans are exposed to microcystin through many pathways, including oral ingestion
442 during recreation or from drinking water, consuming contaminated foods and supplements,
443 dermal contact, and inhalation of aerosols (Carmichael and Boyer 2016). However, the
444 predominant pathway of microcystin exposure to humans is ingestion of contaminated drinking
445 water or ingestion during recreation (Giannuzzi et al. 2011). Communities that rely on untreated
446 drinking water from lakes, reservoirs, and groundwater wells with microcystin concentrations
447 that exceed recommended thresholds for ingestion are particularly vulnerable (Zhang et al.
448 2009b; Ruibal-Conti et al. 2019). Additionally, when microcystin makes its way into domestic
449 water supplies, hygienic activities such as bathing and hand washing become a pathway of
450 exposure through respirable water particles (Benson et al. 2005).

451 Microcystin in animal tissues that humans consume is another cryptic pathway of
452 exposure. In general, tissue concentrations in fish and shellfish are high when the surrounding
453 water column concentrations are high (Ibelings and Chorus 2007; Poste et al. 2011; Flores et al.
454 2018). When microcystin concentrations are high in the water column, consumption of whole
455 animals such as bivalves can result in 8-23.5 times the tolerable daily load for humans as defined
456 by the World Health Organization (Chen and Xie 2005). Preparation method can also affect
457 exposure risk, as boiling animal muscle tissue (e.g., fish fillets) has been shown to release
458 microcystin otherwise bound to phosphate (Berry et al. 2011).

459

460 **Comparing Magnitudes of Pools and Fluxes**

461 *Quantitative Comparison*

462 Through the literature synthesis we identified studies of pools and fluxes from a diversity
463 of inland waters employing a variety of measurement methods and reported units. While it is not
464 feasible to construct a full quantitative cycle using the literature synthesis, we can further
465 synthesize the reported values to compare the magnitude of pools and fluxes and identify poorly
466 parameterized processes. To do this, we used a subset of studies that reported pools and fluxes in
467 consistent and comparable units. For each of these studies, we extracted or calculated mean and
468 standard deviations for pool and flux values reported. For studies without a reported variance, we

469 estimated the standard deviation using the linear relationship between mean and standard
 470 deviation (s.d.) for all pools and fluxes (s.d. = $-1.35 \times 0.99 \times \text{mean}$; $F_{1,61}=327.9$, p-value <0.001 ,
 471 $R^2 = 0.84$). The population of means and standard deviations collected from the literature for a
 472 given pool or flux were used in a random effects model with a restricted maximum likelihood
 473 estimator method to estimate the mean pool or flux magnitude and 95% confidence intervals (CI)
 474 (Figure 4). This analysis was performed using the *metafor* package in R version 4.1.3
 475 (Viechtbauer 2010).

Figure 4. The estimate of the mean magnitude (square) and 95% confidence interval (line) of various pools (top panel) and fluxes (bottom panel) in a random effects model using a subset of studies from the literature with comparable units of measurement. A log scale was used for visualization, and therefore confidence intervals that included zero were set to 0.001 for plotting and the confidence interval crosses the vertical dashed line denoting zero. Mean estimates with a 95% confidence interval not including zero have an asterisk next to the bar. The number of studies (n) contributing to each estimate is displayed above each estimate.

500

501 In general, there were few studies with comparable units for estimating the magnitude of
 502 pools and fluxes and high variance within and among studies (Figure 4). Only six of the fourteen
 503 mean estimates had confidence intervals that did not include zero. Despite this high degree of
 504 uncertainty and variation in measurement methods, some patterns did emerge that can be
 505 cautiously interpreted. The mean concentration of microcystin in sediments ($0.13 \mu\text{g g}^{-1} \text{ d.w.}$, [-

506 0.01, 0.27 CI) was an order of magnitude lower than the mean sediment sorption capacity (1.3
507 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w, [-0.57, 3.27 CI]), potentially indicating that fluxes resulting in loss of microcystin
508 from the sediment pool (e.g., burial, diffusion) can actively reduce concentrations below sorption
509 capacity. However, the estimates for both pools had confidence intervals that included zero. The
510 mean half-life for sediment biodegradation (3.57 days [2.01, 5.13 CI]) was similar to the half-life
511 in the water column (4.67 days [2.028, 7.32 CI]) in this among-study comparison. The mean
512 concentrations in macrophyte tissue (3.45 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w, [-1.58, 8.49 CI]), the epiphyte pool (2.10
513 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w, [1.15, 3.05 CI]), and the sediment biofilm pool (0.35 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w, [-0.81, 1.51 CI])
514 indicate the magnitude of the primary producer reservoir of microcystin not found in the water
515 column pool. For aquatic consumers, the mean zooplankton concentration was the highest of any
516 pool (134.7 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w, [94.5, 175.1 CI]), followed by macroinvertebrates (values only available
517 for oligochaetes, bivalves, a gastropod, and chironomid; 3.75 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w, [1.19, 6.32 CI]). The
518 estimate for whole fish was taken from another meta-analysis that was based on 25
519 measurements (Flores et al. 2018).

520

521 *Consideration of Temporal Dynamics*

522 When cyanobacteria bloom—by definition, an episodic event—the pool of microcystin in
523 the water column and/or biofilm can increase during this period. Given the detrimental effects of
524 microcystin to human health, a great deal of research effort has focused on understanding the
525 temporal dynamics of blooms and toxin production (Rastogi et al. 2015), even during periods of
526 ice cover (Wejnerowski et al. 2018). The seasonality of blooms and toxin production likely also
527 produces strong temporal dynamics in the other pools (e.g., animal and macrophyte tissues) and
528 fluxes (e.g., sedimentation, biodegradation) of microcystin, particularly when coupled with
529 variable turnover times in aquatic ecosystems.

530 Turnover times span many orders of magnitude, from a few minutes for a limiting
531 reactant like microcystin for a biodegrading bacterium to months for animal tissues to years for
532 sediment pools. This mismatch in turnover times allows legacies of past events to shape current
533 ecosystem dynamics (Carpenter and Turner 2000). For organisms, tissue turnover time,
534 microcystin accumulation rates, and toxin metabolism (Schmidt et al. 2014) combine with the
535 availability of microcystin from other pools to dictate storage and persistence of the toxin in the
536 aquatic food web. Organisms in lakes where blooms only occur seasonally may pose less of a

537 threat to humans consuming them depending on the time since the bloom and opportunity for
538 depuration and tissue turnover. On the other hand, the long tissue turnover times of some
539 organisms such as bivalves and fish muscle (Vander Zanden et al. 2015) may result in a “hidden”
540 pathway of human exposure when consumed weeks after a toxic bloom has subsided. Similarly,
541 bloom seasonality in combination with plant phenology and tissue turnover may also affect
542 microcystin accumulation in crops that are irrigated with microcystin-laden water supplies
543 (Romero-Oliva et al. 2014).

544

545 **Future Directions and Research Needs**

546 Constructing a comprehensive biogeochemical microcystin cycle revealed gaps in our
547 understanding of ecosystem-scale microcystin dynamics. Despite the pools and fluxes identified
548 from the literature synthesis, many unknowns remain pertaining to specific mechanisms and
549 environmental factors that favor the movement and accumulation of microcystin within and
550 among the pools. Future investigations of microcystin movement and accumulation in aquatic
551 environments should focus particularly on fluxes to and from the sediment, environmental
552 drivers of biodegradation, and the seasonal dynamics of the aquatic food web pool.

553 Sediments are an active pool of microcystin in freshwater environments (Figure 4)
554 (Zastepa et al. 2015). However, the current handful of ecosystem-level investigations of
555 sediment microcystin fluxes limits our understanding of the magnitude and role sediments play
556 in microcystin dynamics overall. For example, there is evidence indicating microcystin
557 resuspension from sediments is a potential source of microcystin into the water column
558 (Maghsoudi et al. 2015), but it is unclear when, where, and how much this flux contributes to the
559 water column pool. Incorporating sediment-water exchange of microcystin into models and
560 applying these to ecosystem level investigations would generate valuable insight into the role of
561 sediments in microcystin movement and accumulation.

562 Similarly, there is currently little information on the seasonal dynamics and
563 environmental drivers of microcystin biodegradation in both the water column and sediments.
564 While advances have been made in isolating and identifying microcystin-degrading bacteria,
565 additional data are needed to understand the seasonal dynamics and mechanisms that control
566 rates of biodegradation at an ecosystem scale. Accurately quantifying this important loss term in

567 the microcystin cycle will require scaling bottle experiments from a controlled laboratory setting
568 to the whole ecosystem scale which is heterogenous in both space and time.

569 While there are observational studies of microcystin dynamics in consumers in natural
570 environments, much of the information we have regarding microcystin accumulation in aquatic
571 organisms comes from toxicology-type studies with exposure treatments performed in a
572 laboratory setting. Additional study of the duration and magnitude of microcystin accumulation
573 in organism tissues seasonally and long-term would provide valuable insight into the dynamics
574 of the aquatic consumer pool following bloom events. Another avenue of microcystin movement
575 that remains poorly understood are the predominant uptake pathways in aquatic organisms and
576 the role of environmental regulation of these rates. Similarly, the rates of microcystin excretion
577 and egestion are poorly quantified. Further investigations of microcystin fluxes across aquatic-
578 terrestrial interfaces and along the aquatic continuum (i.e., from inland to coastal ecosystems) are
579 also needed to better capture the exogenous inputs available for consumer uptake. For example,
580 limited information exists on microcystin flux via emergent aquatic insects from the aquatic to
581 terrestrial environment (Moy et al. 2016). Similarly, the hydrologic fluxes of microcystin
582 downstream into the marine environment poses a threat to wildlife (Miller et al. 2010) and
583 humans consuming contaminated shellfish (Gibble et al. 2016).

584 Finally, the development of full microcystin budgets for watersheds requires investigators
585 across various fields to report values in a ‘common currency’ that can be incorporated into
586 ecosystem models. For example, measurements of pools need to be in mass per unit area or
587 volume and fluxes in mass per unit area or volume per unit time. While we were able to compare
588 some microcystin pools across the literature ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ d.w.; Figure 3 and 4), measurements reported
589 in this common currency were lacking for some important pools, preventing us from developing
590 a full, quantitative budget.

591

592 **Conclusions**

593 The conceptual biogeochemical model for microcystin that we constructed identified the
594 major pools and fluxes of this toxin for inland waterbodies. From the quantitative synthesis we
595 presented (Figure 4) it is evident that microcystin is present and moves through many
596 components of the ecosystem besides the water column. Given the many fluxes into and out of
597 the water column (e.g., import from upstream, sediment diffusion), the visual presence of bloom

598 is not necessarily indicative of exposure risk for humans. This conceptual model can be used as
599 the framework for developing ecosystem mass balances of microcystin to quantify the transport
600 and transformation of this toxin both in freshwater and marine ecosystems. Adopting the
601 framework of a “microcystin cycle” will not only improve our understanding of processes
602 driving toxin prevalence but will also help to prioritize effective strategies for the management of
603 microcystin exposure risks to humans and wildlife.

604

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